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IMPROVING THE QUALITIES OF PHYSICAL ENDURANCE IN STUDENT YOUTH

Annotation: *The main objectives of physical education are to improve the health of students, their physical development, the acquisition of a system of motor skills and the development of physical qualities. To solve these tasks, depending on the age of the students, work is carried out in different ways with children of primary school age, adolescents and young people. preschool and school age periods are divided into small, medium and large school age, respectively, affecting the rapid emergence of the children's institutional system.*

Keywords: *Physical qualities, sports, wrestling, boxing, endurance, running, physical development, wrestling, physical development, media, active, physical education.*

The practical active actions of people, as well as physical qualities are directly related to the functions (activities) of the organs of the body. That is, all active movements ensure the rapid movement of the human body, that is, respiration, heart rate, blood circulation, digestion of substances in the internal organs, metabolism. On this basis, many biological, chemical and physiological changes take place. Endurance exercises based on such active movements have a special place. Endurance refers to the process of coping, enduring, and overcoming the challenges of social life, physical education classes, sports training, and sports competitions, both large and small. Naturally, such socio-educational features do not arise spontaneously or are not an innate factor. Signs and qualities of endurance require a lot of repetition of exercises, long periods of exercise. Endurance breathing, holding the breath inward, and the habituation of muscles and all joints to perform light and heavy movements are paramount. Endurance traits and qualities are more commonly encountered and defined in the following active actions.

1. In the process of running short, medium and especially long distances in athletics (10-20 km and more) there is difficulty breathing, fatigue of the legs and arms, weakness. In particular, the arms, shoulders, waist and as a result are created opportunities for the above activities to pass easily or endure them.

2. It is natural to get tired to some extent in swimming, football (running for 90 minutes, kicking a ball) and other sports. To overcome and endure them, each trainee needs more exercise.

It is natural that schoolchildren and students get tired in physical education classes (athletics, gymnastics, wrestling, etc.). Because most young people do not have enough physical training and special training. For this reason, first of all, it is necessary to have physical development and special physical training. The concept of socio-cultural living

conditions, physical labor and physical qualities in sports are directly related to each other. That is, in everyday behavior, in the learning process and in physical labor, such as "agile", "light", "agile", "excellent", "strong", "brave", "endurance-endurance". folk expressions are common. In their context, the terms used in science, such as "endurance", "strength", "flexibility", "agility" are understood as physical qualities. These, in turn, are combined with terms and concepts such as "physical training", "physical development", "special physical training", "sportsmanship", "sports form". It will be possible to make some comments about their most important symptoms. Strength is the basis (father) of physical qualities. Because its application and performance characteristics, types are used in all practical activities, as well as in all sports in a unique way, and the need arises. In sports, strength is mainly used in weightlifting, wrestling, boxing, arm strength testing, weightlifting. In the sports mentioned above, the muscles are used to pull, stretch, push, hit, hold (barbell), and so on. actions. At the same time, the characteristic of each sport is the use of slow, fast and fast-power qualities in the performance of technical and tactical movements. Muscle strength (dynamometry, stanometry) and speed of movement (stopwatch, computer, etc.) are the main ones, which are measured by special instruments. The speed of movement (swimming, running, hitting the ball, kicking, etc.) can be related to strength. In other words, swimming, running, kicking the ball into the goal with force, technical and tactical movements, speed and forces are intertwined depends. That is, the speed at which the shoulders, neck, and head are raised, and the slight forward lift while keeping the legs straight, make it easier to pull on the arms. This means that in order to be strong, you also need to acquire the qualities of speed. In our socio-cultural life, a lot of force is used. unload it. There should be more strength in the arms, waist, legs. The technique for doing this activity can also vary. That is, lifting with both hands or carrying in a hug; In rural areas, the terms "wrestler" (strong) and rider-wrestler (light-strong) have long been used in wrestling and kupkari (goat) games. They practice for many years to acquire this quality and physical quality (strong). It uses a variety of tools and methods.

A person who engages in physical activity (sports activities) gradually feels that it is difficult to continue their activities. Sweat begins to flow, redness on the face, discoloration, muscle fatigue, impaired coordination of movements, the sequence of elements of the movement technique, changes in the depth of the rhythm of breathing. In the structure of the performed action additional unnecessary actions appear, are added. This is due to physiological, biochemical and biomechanical changes in the body. Continuation of activity is done at the expense of mental, volitional and other qualities. This condition is called the compensatory fatigue phase.

If, despite the increase in the level of willpower, the intensity of work decreases, we observe the beginning of the phase of fatigue without compensation. Fatigue is a temporary decrease in the ability to work during work (exercise) is called fatigue. It has been proven in practice that fatigue varies from person to person during the same activity. because the development of endurance of each individual is different.

Much attention is paid to the issue of fatigue from the scientific heritage of our ancestor Abu Ali ibn Sina. In the Kitab ul Qanun fit Tib, which began to be written in the

one thousandth year and became a perfect historical scientific work in the one thousand and twenty-fourth year, chronic physical exercise causes fatigue and is divided into four types:

1. Wound fatigue - it feels like a sore on the skin on the face or under the skin.
2. Severe fatigue - in which a person feels heat and relaxation in the body, as if his body is crushed or crushed.
3. Swollen Fatigue - the body is redder than usual and feels like a rash.
4. Weight Loss Fatigue - the person who suffers from it feels drier and drier.

Durability is measured with and without tools. To measure endurance with a tool, it is recommended to run at a certain speed, as well as the time to catch that intensity without loosening (until the speed begins to decrease). Therefore, it is very inconvenient to measure endurance directly. More non-instrumental measurements are used. In sports practice, endurance is assessed based on the time spent running long distances (10,000 m; 20,000 m).

Endurance depends on the functional capacity of a person to perform the required exercises, on the one hand, on the level of mastery of the necessary movement skills and techniques, on the other hand, on the aerobic and anaerobic (oxygenated, non-oxygenated) capabilities of the body. The specificity of the beliefs of the breath is relatively low, they do not depend enough on the external form of action. Therefore, a runner who increases his aerobic capacity with the help of running exercises will also benefit from his endurance when performing other activities, such as rowing, walking, cycling. For example, the coordination structure of walking and running movements and the characteristics of speed and strength often differ. The improvement in speed achieved through training does not have a positive or negative effect on the maximum speed of walking. That is, there is no "migration". Running speed did not affect walking speed change. However, it has been scientifically and practically proven that long-distance training can "move" with each other while walking and running at the same time. Therefore, if we take into account the functional capacity of the autonomic system of the body of the athlete in the performance of coordinated movements, the generalized case, conditionally speaking, "vegetative" exercise opens up a favorable opportunity for "migration" of endurance. However, in each case, the absence of migration depends not only on the energy capacity of the organism, all the qualitative features of the movement, but also on the nature of the coordination of motor skills. Solving specific tasks of general and special endurance requires the performance of the same amount of hard work, of the same size and to the greatest extent possible. It is necessary not to stop exercising, even when fatigue begins to turn into fatigue. This places a high demand on the manifestation of mental readiness.

The development of endurance is carried out by cultivating a love of work, readiness to withstand heavy loads, as well as extreme fatigue. Athletes increase their endurance only when they feel more or less tired during training. This is reflected in the increase in endurance from the outside. Adaptation is determined by the amount of changes and the purpose, the degree of response in the body as a result of training loads. Criteria and components of the load play an important role in cultivating resilience. If we pay attention to the fact that endurance develops during training, the athlete will feel a little tired, it

becomes clear that endurance will not develop if recovery occurs after a very short time after exercise. When the workload is large and performed with a feeling of fatigue, the body begins to adapt to the load, and after a series of exercises, you can see an increase in endurance. Adaptation occurs through the degree of change in the body, the nature of the response to the load, the direction of its scale. Fatigue is not the same in different types of workload. Breathing has been shown to play an important role in endurance. Accordingly, the correctness of the exercise, which is performed in a quiet, rhythmic work, mainly with deep breathing through the nose, has been proven in practice. It is known that the breath, chest, abdomen (abdominal press) and mixed muscles - is obtained through the intervention of the diaphragm. Deep breathing through the mouth is recommended to maximize pulmonary ventilation during strenuous activity. The main focus should be on exhalation, as it is recommended to exhale sharply and deeply so that the oxygenated air in the lungs does not mix with fresh air. In many national folk games, physical qualities such as speed and endurance are nurtured through intense exercise. In such games, the physical load (load) is gradually increased. For example, enlarging the area; reduce the number of players without reducing the area; increase the number of play equipment (sticks, handkerchiefs, doppi, coats, balls, etc.) to extend the running distance; increase the number of barriers; use complex exercises and increase their number, and so on. When these methods are used consistently, the goal is achieved faster. Examples of such physical games are Lamé Crow, Lanka, and Podachi. For example, The Lamé Crow is a relay-type action game. The number of players is equal, and the two teams line up facing each other. Each player takes turns tying one of their legs to the ankle with a bandage (handkerchief or ribbon). The players of both teams shouted "Get ready!" when given the command, they jump on one leg to the line of the opposing team, then remove the bandage from their legs, run backwards, and pass it to the next player on their team. This continues until the last player to bring the game link to the teacher. The team that brings the tie to the teacher first wins. Games that affect certain muscle groups and joints are selected to develop flexibility in 7-8 year olds. These games are mainly played with the help of special sports equipment. Instead of weights, trainees can participate. Active flexibility depends on muscle strength. The tensile properties of muscles change under the influence of the central nervous system. Therefore, flexibility is high when students participate in these games with pleasure. Appropriate exercises should be performed before games that require flexibility. Games such as "kneeling under the knee", "throwing a stick in a circle", "jumping over an obstacle", and "rock play" are recommended to develop flexibility. For example, we recommend to teachers a "stone game" for 7-8 year olds that is fun and effectively increases the quality of flexibility. The participants of the game stand in a circle. Each of them, except for one player, holds five stones in his hands. At the first signal of the teacher, the players throw their stones in front of them and sit back in the center of the circle. According to the second signal, they turn sharply to the initial position and each player tries to get his stone. The player who does not get the stone is considered the loser and the game starts again. The winner is the player who is the most agile, agile and fast-moving, who gets his stone on time. First of all, it should be noted that the development of the child depends on the

environment, how life is organized, upbringing, including physical education. directly related. Growth is unique to young school children. The basis of children's physical education is the promotion of health and proper physical development.

The main objectives of physical education are to improve the health of students, their physical development, the acquisition of a system of motor skills and the development of physical qualities. To solve these tasks, depending on the age of the students, work is carried out in different ways with children of primary school age, adolescents and young people. preschool and school age periods are divided into small, medium and large school age, respectively, affecting the rapid emergence of the children's institutional system. n physiology, the existing system of division of children and adolescents into age periods, separate stages of development, is the basis for school-age children. In pedagogy, the school age is 7-10 years old, 11-14 years old and 15-17 years old.

Teaching children life skills that are vital in a timely manner, the most important of which are walking, running, jumping and throwing skills. The main focus of physical education classes with young school-age children is on the development of vital processes: walking, running, jumping, throwing, correct posture, agility, ability to analyze muscle speed. Proper maintenance of the system of physical activity with school-age children enhances the growth and development of the child's body, stimulates physiological processes. An integral part of physical education is teaching, in which students learn the complexities of learning a variety of skills and movements. The choice of tools and methods in teaching children in physical education classes should be made in a way that is strictly in line with the physical capabilities of students of different ages. At the age of 6, motor skills and abilities begin to develop rapidly. They increase height, muscle strength, improve coordination of movement, improve the amplitude, speed, direction, rhythm, speed, evaluation skills of movement, the ability to analyze movement, to create certain qualities in it. The child begins to understand that the results of movement depend on the qualities of his performance, and then begins to perform movements with endurance, endurance, in order to achieve good results. increases. Experts estimate that cross-country running from 3 km to 45 km is recommended to increase the overall endurance of small school-age children. To this end, it is recommended to include movement games and play exercises in the lessons.

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